

"DIFFERENTIAL ANALYSIS OF NEUROTIC DISORDERS IN IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME AND IMPROVEMENT OF MEDICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT IN THEM".

Gafurova S.Sh.
Yusuphadjaeva S.T.

Assistant of the Department of Neurology with Medical Psychology, Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

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Research purpose : Affected intestine syndrome neurotic violations differential analysis and them medical psychological help improvement .

Research materials and methods : Research works in 2022 during Tashkent Medicine Academy a lot network clinic gastroenterology in the department was eaten . Affected intestine syndrome diagnosis with sick patients analysis done _ Inspection 62 people in the patient take went _ Patients medium age 29 ± 4.5 consists of 24 men , 38 women _ _ was _ Patients two to the group divided without studied: First group - 30 patients used only in TIS standard base treatment and psychopharmacotherapy applied . Second group - 32 patients standard from treatment except psychotherapy applied . Anxiety-phobic violations determination in order to Spielberger-Hanin from the questionnaire was used .

Results and discussions : In the assessment of anxiety-phobic disorders in patients, it was found that patients in group 1 have three different levels of personal anxiety. In particular, 12 patients (40%) had mild anxiety, 10 patients (33.3%) had moderate anxiety, and 8 patients (26.6%) had severe anxiety. After the end of treatment, these indicators were reflected in the following values: mild anxiety in 18 patients (60%), moderate anxiety in 8 patients (26.6%) and severe anxiety in 4 patients (13.3%). Scores for reactive phobic disorders in patients of group 1: mild phobic disorders in 15 patients (50%), moderate phobic disorders in 7 patients (23.3%) and severe phobic disorders in 6 patients (20%). They also reported changes in these parameters after treatment: mild phobic disorders in 20 patients (66.6%), moderate phobic disorders in 5 patients (16.6%) and 3 patients (10 %) severe phobic disorders. Indicators of phobic disorders (group 1) The results of the study showed that in the patients of the first group, severe and moderate forms of anxiety decreased and turned into mild forms, mild anxiety disappeared completely. Anxiety scores before treatment in group 2: mild anxiety in 15 patients (47%), moderate anxiety in 9 patients (28%) and severe anxiety in 8 patients (25%). After treatment in group 2, these scores changed as follows: mild anxiety in 18 patients (56%), moderate

anxiety in 4 patients (13%), severe anxiety in 1 patient (3%) and anxiety in 9 patients (28%) did not bother at all.

Conclusions. In conclusion, it should be noted that the treatment of anxiety observed in patients with irritable bowel syndrome alleviates the course of the disease and prolongs the duration of remissions. The simultaneous use of psychotherapy and psychopharmacotherapy with the main treatment allows to reduce the risk of relapse and recurrence of the disease, restore work capacity and even accelerate recovery from the disease and increase adherence to the main treatment.

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